

Time of day of flowering in wild species of the genus *Oryza*

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Potentially, the most consistent and damaging consequences of climate change for rice could come through the yield-depressing effects of high temperature (Sheehy et al 2006). Anthesis is very susceptible to damage in the 35–40 °C temperature range and exposure for a matter of a few hours during flowering can reduce floral reproduction (Satake and Yoshida 1978, Nishiyama and Satake 1981, Baker et al 1992). A simple model (Sheehy et al 2005) was used to validate the hypothesis that flowering close to dawn or at night could make plants much less vulnerable to high temperature-induced sterility (Nishiyama and Blanco 1980). The time of day when flowering commenced (TDF) in the main stems of 91 *Oryza sativa* and 5 *O. glaberrima* cultivars was studied by Sheehy et al (2005). *O. glaberrima* (Marori) had the earliest TDF of 0830. Of the *O. sativa* cultivars, Chhalangpa had the earliest TDF of 0915.

We decided to determine whether wild rice species flowered close to dawn (0500–0600). Consequently, a total of 61 accessions were selected from IRRI germplasm to represent a wide range of countries with hot climates. Each of the wild species of *Oryza* was included in the study; *O. neocaledonica* was unavailable. Because wild rice cannot be grown in the field, the accessions were grown in a screenhouse at IRRI following appropriate pro-

ocols. The seedlings were transplanted at a spacing of 20 cm × 20 cm into plastic buckets (45.5 cm in diameter and 62.5 cm in height) containing lowland soil. A basal application of 18.2 g per bucket of complete fertilizer (NPK) was applied. Subsequently, 2 g of N were added monthly and the soil was kept saturated throughout the experiment. The main stems of four replicates were observed for TDF on the first and final days of flowering; the difference in the number of days was the time a panicle took to complete (CPF). The time taken for the spikelets to close following flowering (anthesis) was also recorded. To test the consistency of TDF across years, the experiment was conducted in 2002, 2003, and 2004. In 2002, it was found that more accessions could have been observed, so the number of accessions to be germinated was increased from 54 to 61 in 2003. However, in both 2003 and 2004, several of the accessions failed to grow.

In the 3 years of the experiment, seven of the accessions from six wild rice species consistently had TDFs earlier than 0700 (see table). Only one species (*O. alta*) flowered at night. Anthesis lasted for about 2 h; the average for all the accessions in all the years was 114 ± 6 min. A linear regression between TDF on the final day of flowering (y) and TDF on the first day of flowering (x) across all accessions and years ($y = 1.019x - 0.008$; $P < 0.001$) showed

that these TDFs were almost identical. This result suggests that TDF does not vary significantly for a panicle on each of its days of flowering; the panicles took between 3 and 9 d to complete flowering (see table). The study showed that wild rice species are a potential source of early TDF genes.

References

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Mean and standard error of the earliest time of day when flowering commenced (TDF) and the number of days a panicle took to complete flowering (CPF) of wild rice species. (Observations made in 3 different years; data arranged from early to late TDF in 2002.)

Accession no.	Wild rice species	2002				2003				2004			
		TDF (h)		CPF (d)		TDF (H)		CPF (day)		TDF (H)		CPF (d)	
		Mean	SE ^a	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE
80740	<i>O. granulata</i>	0500	0	7	0.7	0611	7	8	1	0600	0	6	0.0
100820	<i>O. ridleyi</i>	0528	10	9	2.4	0600	0	5	0				
101424	<i>O. eichingeri</i>	0545	4	4	1.0	0557	1	5	0	0600	0	6	0.7
104985	<i>O. latifolia</i>					0541	3	5	1	0600	0	7	0.0
105144	<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	0600	0	9	0.7	0600	0	5	0				
105156	<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	0600	0	7	1.2					0730	44	5	1.0
106241	<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	0600	0	7	0.7					0631	1	6	0.0
80720	<i>O. officinalis</i>	0600	0	4	0.6	0601	0	4	0	0600	0	7	0.0
101414	<i>O. officinalis</i>	0600	0	7	0.6	0937	3	5	0	0915	0	6	0.0
100974	<i>O. longiglumis</i>	0630	14	9	0.9	0712	5	5	1				
101081	<i>O. minuta</i>	0650	8	5	0.8	0700	0	6	1	0700	0	6	0.0
103912	<i>O. barthii</i>	0705	10	5	0.5	0830	0	4	0	1032	1	7	0.0
103421	<i>O. rhizomatis</i>	0705	5	7	0.8								
100885	<i>O. latifolia</i>	0712	29	5	0.6	0541	2	6	1	0600	0	5	0.0
100930	<i>O. longistaminata</i>	0808	2	5	0.3	0935	6	5	0	0951	12	7	0.7
89245	<i>O. eichingeri</i>	0820	12	5	0.6	0715	3	5	0	0700	0	7	0.3
104117	<i>O. barthii</i>	0825	3	3	0.3	1018	2	5	1	1006	10	4	0.3
104981	<i>O. barthii</i>	0836	13	3	0.0	0906	12	4	0				
104119	<i>O. barthii</i>	0843	11	3	0.3	0956	1	5	0	1022	8	5	0.3
102175	<i>O. nivara</i>	0845	19	3	0.3	1007	9	5	1	1000	0	6	0.8
104084	<i>O. barthii</i>	0845	17	4	0.0	1003	1	6	0	1026	33	4	0.3
86541	<i>O. meridionalis</i>	0905	17	9	5.5	0945	6	6	0	1030	0	4	0.3
102167	<i>O. nivara</i>	0905	15	4	0.6	0955	4	6	1	0932	1	3	0.0
105666	<i>O. glumaepatula</i>	0907	8	5	0.5					1046	14	6	0.6
102176	<i>O. nivara</i>	0912	20	3	0.3	1131	11	5	1	1050	20	6	0.6
105570	<i>O. brachyantha</i>	0919	23	3	0.3					0921	3	5	0.0
102163	<i>O. nivara</i>	0921	15	4	1.8	1004	3	4	0	0600	0	5	0.0
103534	<i>O. barthii</i>	0922	11	3	0.3	1000	12	4	0	1020	8	4	1.7
104433	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	0922	16	5	0.5	0945	6	5	0	1007	2	7	0.3
100940	<i>O. barthii</i>	0925	2	3	0.0	0933	2	4	0	1001	8	4	0.3
105925	<i>O. nivara</i>	0925	0	4	0.0	0832	1	5	0				
104447	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	0927	34	6	1.7	0927	7	4	0	0933	1	6	0.6
104112	<i>O. barthii</i>	0937	8	4	0.3	0915	6	5	1	0942	15	6	0.3
102113	<i>O. barthii</i>	0942	16	4	0.3					0930	0	5	0.0
104408	<i>O. nivara</i>	0957	29	5	1.0	0922	5	5	0	1100	0	5	0.0
104061	<i>O. barthii</i>	1003	30	4	0.3	0945	18	4	0	1007	16	5	1.3
104405	<i>O. nivara</i>	1010	2	3	0.0	0921	11	5	0				
89145	<i>O. barthii</i>	1030	81	7	0.3	0937	3	5	0	0600	0	6	0.0
106207	<i>O. barthii</i>	1030	14	3	0.3	0959	2	4	0	1035	0	4	0.0
104402	<i>O. nivara</i>	1031	19	3	0.3	1000	0	5	1	1043	5	5	0.0
104399	<i>O. sativa/O. nivara</i>	1050	6	5	0.6	0933	4	4	0	1045	0	5	0.0
105607	<i>O. punctata</i>	1052	12	4	0.6	1048	6	5	0	1001	1	4	0.0
103897	<i>O. punctata</i>	1056	4	6	1.3	1057	12	6	1	1041	1	6	0.3
88796	<i>O. glumaepatula</i>	1107	14	5	0.3	1010	4	6	0	1030	0	5	0.8
105180	<i>O. punctata</i>	1108	9	4	0.6	1107	2	6	0	1130	0	6	0.0
104976	<i>O. longistaminata</i>	1116	30	6	0.7	1330	10	5	0				
105424	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	1135	73	4	0.3	1104	1	5	0				
101236	<i>O. brachyantha</i>	1141	42	5	0.6					0958	15	4	0.0
103913	<i>O. longistaminata</i>	1148	63	3	0.3	1311	4	5	0				
105206	<i>O. longistaminata</i>	1215	70	4	0.7								
105563	<i>O. longistaminata</i>	1220	63	4	0.0								
101198	<i>O. longistaminata</i>	1232	71	4	0.0	1334	7	6	1				
106454	<i>O. longistaminata</i>	1330	0	5	0.3	1307	3	4	0				
100882	<i>O. australiensis</i>	1600	26	5	0.9					1551	1	5	0.5
100161	<i>O. alta</i>	2145	0	4	0.0	2233	2	4	1				
105273	<i>O. australiensis</i>					1556	10	5	1	1505	0	6	0.0
106001	<i>O. barthii</i>					1000	2	5	0	1026	4	4	0.3
100931	<i>O. barthii</i>					1041	7	3	0	1025	7	4	0.0
101429	<i>O. eichingeri</i>					1100	0	5	0	1052	2	6	0.0
101411	<i>O. meridionalis</i>					1128	1	6	0	1032	1	4	0.3
105623	<i>O. nivara</i>					1113	3	4	0	1127	1	6	0.7

^aif data were absent in 2003 and 2004, it was because the accession failed to grow. *O. meyeriana* failed to grow in each of the years. The flowering pattern of *O. schlechteri* was too erratic to include in this table. ^bStandard error in minutes.